

TEMPERATURE EFFECTS ON A COMPOSITE REPAIR

R. Boykett and K. Walker

*DSTO, Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory, Airframes and Engines Division
506 Lorimer St, Fishermens Bend, Victoria, 3207, Australia*

SUMMARY: The first bonded composite repair to primary aircraft structure in the Royal Australian Air Force has required comprehensive substantiation. A 48 mm long crack in a wing skin was repaired with a boron fibre epoxy resin patch. Successful validation tests on representative specimens included static residual strength tests at ambient, -40, and +110 degrees Celsius. Residual strains in specimens induced by the bonding cure cycle (80°C) were significant, but were slightly relaxed after fatigue loading. Variation in the frequency of this cyclic loading and raising the temperature did not clearly effect crack growth. The testing program verified the durability and damage tolerance of the repair, thus preventing the scrapping of the aircraft wing. The results suggest that thermal effects, on the integrity of the repaired structure, are less severe than predicted in the current analytic approaches used by AMRL and the RAAF.

KEYWORDS: boron/epoxy composite, aircraft repair, strength tests, crack growth, temperature effects, airworthiness certification

INTRODUCTION

A supersonic F-111C aircraft of the Royal Australian Air Force has been repaired by the application of a Boron Fibre - Epoxy Resin composite patch over a 48 mm long fatigue crack in the lower wing skin. Calculations¹ of the residual strength for the cracked structure predicted a value more than 30% below the original Design Limit Stress, thus compromising flight safety. The repair was designed and applied in accordance with the new RAAF Engineering Standard C5033 to restore flight safety. The validation of such a critical repair to aircraft structure is an important part of the assessment of the aircraft's airworthiness prior to its return to full operational service. In this case, validation by AMRL consisted of two independent methods ; a stress analysis^{2,3} using Finite Element Methods, and experimental testing of representative specimens⁴.

The experimental testing program successfully used three different specimen designs in 28 tests under a range of configurations. This paper concentrates on the performance of medium-sized "Panel" specimens (190 x 300 mm test-section).

DESCRIPTION

The wingskin has raised sections on the inner surface that act as integral stiffeners and attachment lands for the five wing spars⁵. The location of the cracking in the lower wing skin is shown below in Figure 1 in an area below the forward auxiliary spar at a distance of 281.23 inches (7.143 m) from the wing root, known as FASS 281. At this point, the thickness of the integral stiffener is reduced from 8.2 mm to the local skin thickness (3.6 mm minimum) over a length of 20 mm. This depression allows for fuel flow between adjacent bays of the wing-box fuel tank and loss of spanwise stiffness is compensated by two adjacent integral stiffeners.

Figure 1: Location of cracking on the F-111 lower wing-skin, at FASS 281, showing also the outline of the repair patch.

Figure 2: Local geometry of the wing skin in the vicinity of the fuel-flow passage, showing the location of cracking and reference axes used in the text. X is spanwise direction, Y is chordwise direction, Z is upwards.

The crack growth direction was chordwise, driven by the principal stress from the wing bending loads (predominantly tension in the lower skin). The local asymmetrical geometry leads to a significant stress concentration and also to out-of-plane secondary bending at the location where the cracking occurred.

The repair¹ consisted of a composite patch, 470 x 320 mm, bonded to the external surface of the wing skin using Cyanamid FM 73 structural film adhesive. The patch was 14 plies of uniaxial boron fibre epoxy resin (5521-4) pre-preg tape in a $[0_3, \pm 45, 0_2]_s$ lay-up. The edges of the patch were tapered and the corners chamfered to reduce the peel and shear stresses in the adhesive. In the first step, the patch was fully cured with a layer of film adhesive on the faying surface, using a mould of the wing skin contour. The faying surface of the wing skin (including fastener heads) was then carefully solvent cleaned of oil, paint and protective finishes, then grit-blasted with aluminium oxide, before being treated with an adhesion promoter (brush-applied A-187 silane coupling agent) to ensure a good bond surface. The patch was then applied to the structure with a second layer of film adhesive before being cured (101.3 kPa, 80°C) for eight hours. Non-destructive inspection using ultrasonic A-scan techniques confirmed the integrity of the patch and adhesive bondline.

PREDICTED PERFORMANCE

Fracture mechanics calculations of the residual strength assumed a straight-fronted through-thickness crack as shown shaded in Figure 2. The residual strength, σ_{RES} , can be estimated from the simple formula :

$$K_C = \sigma_{RES} \sqrt{(\pi a)} \quad (1)$$

For a handbook value of $K_C = 46 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ and a crack half-length, a , of 24 mm, this gives an estimate of 168 MPa for the residual strength of the wing at this location, a significant reduction from the Design Limit Stress of 256 MPa established for this area¹.

This estimate is conservative in two respects. First, the effective fracture toughness for the skin material (2024-T851 aluminium alloy, LT orientation) was found experimentally⁴ to be in the range 57 - 62 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, which is significantly higher than the handbook value used above. Secondly, the beneficial effect of the spar bridging the crack has been ignored.

Because the mechanical properties of adhesives and of polymer-matrix composites vary significantly with temperature, and because of the significant mismatch in the thermal coefficients of expansion between the composite patch (3×10^{-6} per °C) and the underlying metallic skin (23×10^{-6} per °C), three load/temperature cases were identified⁶ for demonstrations of adequate static strength.

- At high temperature (110°C), the design limit stress was 143 MPa.
- At ambient (23°C) and low (-40°C) temperature conditions, the design limit stress of 256 MPa was applicable.

The predicted failure or residual stress of the repaired structure can be calculated from the patch repair design⁷. The stress intensity factor, K_∞ , is evaluated for the design condition of elastic behaviour of a one-sided supported repair :

$$K_\infty = \sigma_{design} \sqrt{\frac{E_i t_i \lambda \eta}{G}} \quad (2)$$

Where E_i and t_i are the aluminium adherend's modulus and thickness, λ is the inverse of the elastic transfer length, and η and G are the adhesive's thickness and shear modulus.

Assuming that K_∞ is directly proportional to the applied load and that the aluminium fracture toughness, K_{IC} , is $46 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, the residual stress can be estimated from:

$$\sigma_{RES} = \frac{K_{IC}}{K_\infty} \sigma_{design} \quad (3)$$

Hence, predicted failure stresses for the panel specimens can be stated for the temperatures of -40°C (438 MPa) and 23°C (359 MPa), which both exceed the design limit value (256 MPa). However, the manufacturer's data for FM 73 adhesive is not intended for temperatures above 82°C , preventing an estimate for the 110°C condition.

The influence of temperature on crack propagation behaviour after repair with a bonded composite patch is complicated by the following factors:

1. The effective stress ratio, R , is increased due to the thermal residual stress. This will be tension in the aluminium structure and compression in the boron repair in this wing skin example for all conditions below the 80°C cure temperature.
2. The patching efficiency changes because the properties of the adhesive vary considerably with temperature. With an increase in temperature, the shear modulus, G , and the yield strength, τ_p , of the adhesive are reduced and the patching efficiency is also reduced. Note, however, that this effect is opposed by the thermal residual stress.
3. The crack propagation properties of the alloy structure may change with temperature, although this is not significant in this wing skin example over the validation temperature range of -40°C to 110°C .
4. The loading frequency is a potential factor because the time spent at high load is increased with a decrease in frequency and this is the point where the adhesive is loaded into the plastic region in this repair example. Creep effects may also occur at elevated temperature

The thermal residual stress is driven by the difference in the co-efficients of thermal expansion, α , for the bonded materials and the deviation from the cure temperature. However, the aluminium wing structure is only heated in the repair zone, being constrained by the surrounding material. An effective α can be calculated^{7,8} from:

$$\alpha_{eff} = \frac{\alpha(1+\nu)}{2} \quad (4)$$

In this example for aluminium, Poisson's ratio, $\nu = 0.3$ and $\alpha = 23 \times 10^{-6}$ per $^\circ\text{C}$, giving a value for α_{eff} of 14.95×10^{-6} per $^\circ\text{C}$.

SPECIMEN DESIGN

The loading on this cracked section of the aircraft wing skin is predominantly uni-axial tension/compression induced from wing bending loads. Hence, the design of representative specimens⁴ was intended for testing in uniaxial servo-hydraulic testing machines under closed-loop load control. This allowed the application of static loads and cyclic (spectrum and constant amplitude) loads.

Aluminium “panel” specimens were machined from the same alloy as the wing skins, but were not brake-formed, chemical milled or shot-peened. The raised lands of the local geometry in the repair zone were reproduced, including the fastener holes’ size and pitch. The fastener holes conveniently allowed the attachment of a sliding stiffener to prevent the specimen buckling under compressive loads. The test-section width (190 mm) was sufficient to allow crack growth to extend beyond the side stiffeners (95 mm tip to tip crack length) without significant influence from edge effects. The size of the specimen was intended to be small enough to be fitted within an environmental chamber that would allow testing under controlled temperatures. Later tests⁴ used an array of infra-red lamps, controlled by thermocouples, to achieve a better temperature distribution in the test section without enclosing the specimen.

Figure 3: Panel specimen. View onto side representing upper surface of lower wing skin. Boron patch, shown shaded, is bonded to lower surface.

The introduction of the crack defect in the specimen was achieved by creating a small notch in the centre of the side representing the upper surface of the lower wing skin using Electro Discharge Machining. The specimen was then loaded under constant amplitude cyclic tension until a crack appeared the end of the notch and then grew to the required length.

Patching was carried out on cracked specimens in the same manner as the repair on the aircraft, with some exceptions. The repair patch designed for the panel is significantly smaller (190 x 290 mm) than that used on the aircraft (320 x 470 mm); there is no taper at the sides and the chamfer is smaller at the ends, but more importantly, there is less overlap in the length. This is a very conservative approach, giving a measure of the damage tolerance of the repair design either during application or later in service. For convenience, the specimens were autoclave cured under vacuum, whereas the aircraft repair used a positive pressure bag.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Static Strength Tests

The results of static residual strength tests are summarised below in Figure 4. The residual strength (stress in MPa) is calculated to be the failure load divided by the nominal cross-sectional area, ignoring the patch and crack.

These results confirm the prediction that a repair is needed to restore the strength of a specimen with a 40 mm long crack to greater than Design Limit Load.

The residual strength of repaired specimens exceeded DUL, but did not vary significantly when the temperature was reduced from ambient to -40°C , although this was an increase as predicted.

Figure 4: Static strength performance of panel specimens. Design Limit Load is shown for 23°C and -40°C case; at 110°C , DLL is 143 MPa.

The temperature gradient across the specimen test section during the cold test (-40°C) ranged from -16.3°C to -42.2°C , while during the hot test (110°C) it ranged from 83.0°C to 119.4°C . The maximum values were at the centre of the test section due to heat transfer from the ends of the specimen into the grips of the testing machine. This temperature range did not significantly change predicted values for the cold test, but was large enough to be quite important at the higher temperature test. The adhesive used in this repair has degraded performance at elevated temperatures; shear modulus, G , is reduced by over 65% when the temperature is increased from 24°C to its maximum rated 82°C , and also the glass transition temperature is less than 110°C .

The hot test was repeated at a later date on another specimen using an improved environmental chamber that limited the temperature range in the test section to between 105°C and 112°C . This specimen had already been used for fatigue loading, with the crack grown to 69.4 mm after 50,000 simulated flight hours. The crack propagated to failure under a load of 204.7 kN (equivalent to 247 MPa), exceeding both the Design and Ultimate stress for the high temperature load case. This is a remarkable result for a specimen, already degraded by extensive fatigue cycling, under a severe load environment and reinforces the result from the previous hot test.

Residual Thermal Strain Tests

An array of electrical resistance strain gauges was fitted to some specimens, mostly on the boron repair patch along the spanwise centreline, over the crack and also at the end of the patch. With the gauges applied before the patch was bonded to the specimen, the thermal residual stresses in the specimen could be measured after the cure was completed. Unfortunately, the response of gauges at the end of the patch, over the ply terminations, was inconsistent and unreliable.

When strain surveys of the instrumented panel specimens were taken at ambient (23°C) and then the cure temperature (80°C), two results were evident, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Strain distribution in the patch (the crack in this specimen was 2 mm off-centre). Data for 80°C is shown dashed, Data at 25% DLL is shown with markers.

- The relative strain distribution (in the repair patch) in the local area over the crack was not shown to differ significantly when the temperature increased.

However, in combination with extensive cyclic fatigue loading the residual strain in the patch tended to relax slightly. NDI inspections of fatigue loaded specimens indicated an unbond over a small distance (~ 3 mm) either side of the crack; this remained stable as the crack length increased.

- The magnitude of the thermal residual strain has clearly changed.

At a temperature of 23°C, the “far-field” spanwise residual strain (remote from local geometry effects) was -548 μE in the boron patch and +531 μE in the aluminium panel. The residual tensile strain in the aluminium has the potential to enhance crack growth under fatigue loading conditions. When the temperature was raised to 80°C, these values changed to +137 μE and +1225 μE respectively, which is what would be expected for these materials prior to bonding. The same increase in strain ($690 \pm 5 \mu\text{E}$ for both materials) indicated that the

adhesive bond remained intact over this temperature range and compatibility insured that the whole specimen behaved as a homogenous item.

The individual coefficients of thermal expansion, α , were measured during other tests⁴ in this program for the boron patch lay-up and the aluminium alloy. Over the temperature range of -15°C to $+84^{\circ}\text{C}$, the aluminium specimen α was 21×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and for the boron epoxy patch lay-up α was 2.95×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This compared well with the published values for 2024-T851 Aluminium (23×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and for uniaxial boron epoxy (4.1×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$), when allowing for a reduced expansion from the $\pm 45^{\circ}$ plies in the lay-up.

A patched specimen could then be expected to have an average of these two values (12×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The effective co-efficient of thermal expansion measured for the repaired specimen was $690 / 57 = 12.1 \times 10^{-6}$ per $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The amount of residual strain in these repaired test specimens will be more severe than that experienced on the repaired aircraft where the surrounding wing structure constrains expansion under increased temperatures. An effective co-efficient of thermal expansion, for the wing skin, was calculated to be 14.95×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (see section 3). Other tests⁹ at AMRL measured an experimental value for the repair zone on an uncracked, unpatched F-111C wing skin to be 6×10^{-6} per $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This experimental figure is significantly lower than predictions based on Finite Element Methods³ and previous analytic work^{8,10}.

Fatigue Crack Growth Tests

Cyclic loads were applied to specimens as a fatigue spectrum developed¹¹ from flight data for the F-111C fleet in the RAAF. This cycle-by-cycle spectrum contained over 36,000 load points per block of 500 simulated flight hours. It should be noted that the crack growth was not halted by the application of the repair patch to the representative specimens. However, the crack growth rate in repaired specimens was approximately constant, at 0.7 mm per 1000 test hours, less than 3% of that in unrepaired specimens.

Fatigue testing conditions included temperatures at ambient (23°C) and elevated (80°C), and cyclic loading frequencies of 0.5 Hz and 5.0 Hz. Results for crack growth in two panel specimens, under different conditions are shown in Figure 6.

Estimated crack growth rates, calculated from linear regression, give an average of 0.72 mm per 1000 hours, which is similar to the previous tests at ambient temperature. The results did not show a consistent effect of loading frequency or temperature; the variability in crack growth rate is within the bounds of any limited fatigue experiment. Insensitivity to test temperature has been observed¹² in patched, cracked specimens although later work¹³ showed a small increase in crack growth rate with an increase in test temperature. This increase is less than that predicted by theory and may be due to differences between static and dynamic properties of the adhesive.

Figure 6: Crack growth comparisons at 23°C and 80°C, and 0.5 and 5.0 Hz. Data for 80°C is shown dashed, Data for 5.0 Hz is shown with markers.

DISCUSSION

The static mechanical properties of film adhesives such as FM-73 are known to vary markedly with temperature. The large difference in thermal coefficient of expansion for Aluminium alloy and Boron Epoxy implies large residual stresses when bonded together. The combination of these two factors could be expected to significantly influence a repair to a supersonic aircraft wing skin. The experimental results indicate a lack of sensitivity to both temperature (under static and dynamic loading) and loading frequency. This suggests that there is scope to reduce conservatism inherent in the current accepted and proven design analysis^{7,8} developed jointly by AMRL and the RAAF. The thermal mismatch has been found to be far lower than predicted, in a full-sized wing, and this is attributed to the actual level of constraint of the structure. This adds another significant factor to the conservatism of the test specimen results.

Baker¹⁰ suggests that one difficulty with the models and analyses that currently over-estimate the thermal effects (particularly under cyclic loading) may be the use of static rather than dynamic mechanical properties for the adhesive. The use of elastic formulae may also be a factor; both these aspects are under investigation at AMRL.

CONCLUSION

A series of static and fatigue tests were successfully conducted on representative specimens of a bonded composite repair to primary aircraft structure. The results substantiate the repair and confirm that current analytic approaches over-estimate the effects of test temperature and loading frequency. Further work is required to fully understand the complex mechanisms involved with these bonded composite repairs; this will lead to improved analysis techniques which reduce unnecessary conservatism.

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